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Dnmt1 deletion results in Xist activation.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We demonstrate here control of the non-coding RNA Xist by Dnmt1 using targeted gene deletion in human cells. We suggest the data together describe specific function of the DNA methylation machinery in control of gene expression and transcription of the DNA executed by Xist in somatic cells.

Citations

1. Panning, B. and Jaenisch, R., 1996. DNA hypomethylation can activate Xist expression and silence X-linked genes. *Genes & development*, 10(16), pp.1991-2002.